

PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACHES AND FORMATION OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT "INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY GRADES" THROUGH AN ELECTRONIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: In the modern world, there is a fairly large amount of information flow that surrounds us everywhere and we are faced with the need for early learning of information technologies and computer science from the initial stage of training. Every teacher should use all opportunities to ensure that children learn with interest, understand and experience the attractive aspects of computer science, its possibilities in improving mental abilities, in overcoming difficulties. The use of non-traditional, non-standard forms of education, in particular game technologies, has a beneficial effect on the educational process.

Keywords: game, technology, computer science, primary school student, learning method, thinking, memory.

ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ И ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НАУЧНЫХ ЗНАНИЙ ПРИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ПРЕДМЕТА «ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ» ЧЕРЕЗ ЭЛЕКТРОННУЮ СРЕДУ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация: В современном мире достаточно большой объем информационного потока, который окружает нас повсюду и перед нами становится необходимостью раннего изучения информационных технологий и информатике уже начиная с начальной ступени обучения. Каждому педагогу необходимо использовать все возможности для того, чтобы дети учились с интересом, осознали и испытали притягательные стороны информатике, ее возможности в совершенствовании умственных способностей, в преодолении трудностей. Применение нетрадиционных, нестандартных форм обучения и философский подход при дистанционном обучении, в частности игровых технологий, благотворно сказывается на учебном процессе. В данной статье

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рассмотрены философские подходы и формирование научных знаний при преподавании предмета «Информационные технологии в начальных классах» через электронную среду обучения

Ключевые слова: игра, технологии, информатика, младший школьник, метод обучения, мышление, память.

Introduce

The main activity of primary school age is play. The memorization process is most strongly associated with the predominance of visual-figurative thinking of the younger child, which requires many “bright” and emotionally charged teaching techniques and methods. Gaming technology can be such a means.

Gaming technology refers to activities organized during the learning process, the purpose of which is the development of cognitive interest through the emotional coloring of gaming actions based on imitative or symbolic modeling of the objects being studied. Gaming technology contributes to the emergence of interest not only in the acquisition of certain knowledge, but also in its independent acquisition, causing in younger schoolchildren the need for self-education and self-improvement; gaming technologies can be considered as a means of developing the cognitive activity of schoolchildren.

Teachers teaching computer science and ICT need to possess not only knowledge from their subject area, but also gaming technologies, which in turn will help increase the efficiency and productivity of the lesson. For example, when studying the topic “Algorithm and Performers,” you can offer a game with a fairy tale character or a robot who needs help (making tea for guests, ironing a shirt, etc.)

You can also offer travel lessons, treasure hunting, or take the plot of the popular TV show “Where is the logic?”, “Smart Men and Clever Girls,” competition lessons. To enhance the emotional component of the lesson, you can invite fairy-tale or cartoon characters, receive letters, video messages, etc.

Every teacher strives to structure his lesson in such a way that the student is interested throughout the lesson.

If we consider the subject of computer science, we will notice that at first glance it is in a more advantageous position than other disciplines, since modern children are attracted to computers, children view them as something entertaining that does not require the use of any skills to perform practical tasks. lesson objectives.

It is worth noting that in a computer science lesson you have to not only perform practical work on a computer, but also absorb theoretical knowledge. Therefore, I was faced with the question of how to make teaching computer science for primary schools the most interesting and interesting and at the same time, so that productive learning takes place in the lesson.

To do this, I studied the psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature of primary school age and came to the conclusion that at primary school age the leading activity is a game, and in a computer science lesson, game technologies can be used to obtain the highest degree of assimilation of the material.

The educational standard of the new generation identifies the objective need to prepare primary school students for life and activities in the information society, and emphasizes the importance of the informatization process in the domestic education system [4]. Informatization of primary education is a complex dynamic process, the tasks of which at this moment are: increasing the efficiency of the learning process for younger schoolchildren based on the use of electronic educational resources while respecting the age and psychological and pedagogical characteristics of children of this age; the formation of computer literacy among primary school students as a necessary component of the educational, cognitive and educational process of school education; the use of ICT as a leading tool for universal educational activities [3]; creation in primary school of methodological conditions for students to master information literacy and elements of information culture, the formation and effective use of the information and educational environment by each participant in the educational process [5].

The solution to all of the above problems of informatization of primary education falls on the shoulders of the primary school teacher. If previously there were discussions about who should carry out the systematic process of developing computer literacy among primary school students - a computer science teacher or a primary school teacher, now, with the transition to a new educational standard (2009), this issue has been completely removed. Only a primary school teacher, using an arsenal of all educational subjects, carrying out interdisciplinary and multifunctional activities, has the opportunity to implement the requirements of the standard and use ICT as a tool for developing universal educational actions (cognitive, regulatory and communicative) in younger schoolchildren, provided for by the second generation standard, ensuring mastery of key competencies that form the basis of the ability to learn.

When incorporating gaming technologies into the educational process, it is necessary to take into account the following methodological recommendations: first of all, decide on the goal that we want to achieve. It is also important to determine what skill or skill will be developed during the game. Which stage of the game should you focus on? Next, you need to ask the following question: how many students will take part in the game?

After preliminary preparation, one should proceed to the material and technical support of gaming technology; if didactic material is needed for the game, it is necessary to consider its use and method of production.

- Most often, most inexperienced teachers make the mistake of spending too much time familiarizing themselves with the rules of the game or the rules are too complex for students.

- You should also think through and discuss clearer time frames, since children most often have a desire to return to the game several times.

- Next, you should think about at what stage you need to use the game. This need will manifest itself primarily based on didactic and pedagogical goals.

- Due to the age characteristics of children of primary school age, it is necessary to involve all children in the class.

- You should also consider possible adjustments to the game during the lesson, so as not to “lose” the interest and activity of the children.

- For better results, you need to think through the main part of the game, and then you can use the same game to explain other material.

- The conclusion should be clearly and with commentary on the results of the game.

- The most important thing is to think about what conclusion the students will draw for themselves at the end of the game.

Proficiency in gaming technologies for a teacher teaching computer science in elementary school is simply necessary, since in elementary school lessons some structural components of the lesson are replaced by gaming technologies, they can even be applied not only in lessons explaining new material, consolidating, but also in lessons for correcting knowledge and even in control class.

Conclusion

When using gaming technologies in computer science lessons and other lessons, the teacher should be most careful in selecting the material so that every student, regardless of his level of preparedness, takes an active part in the educational process. This is necessary so that he becomes interested in the subject and unexpectedly notices that during the game he learns and applies the acquired knowledge in an unusual situation.

Also, using gaming technologies, the student can develop curiosity, concentration, and contribute to the formation of independent mental activity.

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